

pH and Sorption of Mono-Nitrophenols by Alumina. Part. IV

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Change in the sorption behaviour of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols with chromatographic alumina of varying surface pH (pH 3.5-11.5) in non-aqueous systems has been investigated. The enhanced adsorption with pH, desorption behaviour and liquid-solid adsorption chromatography (LSAC) of the solutes is described.

HYDRONIUM-ION concentration has been found to be a significant factor in the adsorption of various organic compounds by alumina¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our work^{3,4}, attention is now focussed on the nature of sorption of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols on Brockmann alumina, pretreated with HCl-acid and aq. caustic soda. The pertinent literature⁵⁻⁸ shows that possibly no work has been made on the lines described in this paper.

Experimental

Substrate :

Brockmann alumina (S. Merck, India), pretreated with HCl-acid* and aq NaOH of varying strengths, has been used as substrate. The procedure adopted for the preparation of basic alumina samples is summarised in Table 1.

Reagents and Apparatus :

The solutes, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols (to be shown as ONP, MNP and PNP) were the BDH products, which were recrystallised with ethanol and water (ONP), toluene (MNP) and water (PNP). The solvents used were the AR BDH products which were distilled before use.

"Systronics" pH meter (Type 322, accuracy $\pm 1\%$) and "Spekol spectrophotometer" (Carl-Zeiss) were used for measurements. The glass apparatus used were of corning/pyrex make, and calibrated before use.

All the experiments were done at $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

Procedure :

Weighed amounts (0.25 g) of alumina of specific

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF BASIC ALUMINA SAMPLES

pH of alumina prepared	pH of alumina initially taken	Initial amount of alumina : 100 g (pH 8.6)		Period of mechanical shaking	pH of the wash-liquid.
		Time of contact after shaking: 10 min.			
9.5	8.6	200 ml of 0.02 N-NaOH.	50 min.	10.0-10.5	
10.0	8.6	200 ml of 0.1 N-NaOH.	20 min.	10.5-11.0	
10.6	8.6	200 ml of 0.1 N-NaOH.	50 min.	11.2-11.8	
11.5	10.6	200 ml of 2 N-NaOH.	50 min.		

* pH of the wash-liquid was not determined, since the pH was above 12.

pH were taken in well-stoppered 25-ml volumetric flasks. These were then shaken with nitrophenol solution (25 ml each) of known concentrations for 24 hours at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ in a thermostat. After attainment of equilibrium, the equilibrium concentrations of the solutes in dioxane and methanol were estimated colorimetrically at 400 nm by developing colour with aq NaOH.

The benzene solutions of the nitrophenols were poured on water containing the alkali, the solvent evaporated on water bath, and estimated colorimetrically.

Desorption studies of the solutes adsorbed on alumina were carried out as described earlier⁸.

Results and Discussion

The results of adsorption are shown in Table 2 and presented graphically in Figs. 1 and 2. Using

alumina of various surface pH as substrate, it is observed that :

- i) From dioxane solution, the favourable range of adsorption of PNP is pH 6.0-11.5. MNP is not adsorbed at all by the substrates. ONP hardly shows 10% adsorption in the pH range 6.0-8.6 which increases to 15% at pH 11.5 (Table 2).
- ii) The solutes are quantitatively adsorbed from benzene at pH 3.5-11.5 within 5 minutes.
- iii) From methanol, PNP (pH 6.0-8.6) and ONP (pH 3.5-8.6) show some adsorption but MNP has no affinity for the substrates.
- iv) Under the dilutions taken, the compounds have negligible adsorption from water.

TABLE 2—pH AND ADSORPTION OF MONO-NITROPHENOLS FROM DIOXANE AND METHANOL. ($30 \pm 1^\circ$ C, 24 hrs)

Solvent	Initial concentration (mg/l).	pH of alumina and amount adsorbed (mg/1/g).							
		pH 3.5 PNP	ONP	pH 6.0 PNP	ONP	pH 8.6 PNP	ONP	pH 11.5 PNP	ONP
Dioxane	80.0	2.5	No adsorption	20.5	No adsorption	21.7	5.5	48.0	6.4
	60.0	1.9		15.5		16.5	1.2	38.0	6.0
	40.0	1.5		14.3		14.8	1.0	28.0	4.5
	30.0	1.4		14.0		14.0	0.8	22.6	3.5
	20.0	1.3		10.5		10.5	0.5	16.0	2.0
	10.0	0.6		5.5		5.5	—	8.6	0.5
Methanol	80.0	No adsorption	3.7	11.7	8.8	8.0	7.2	No adsorption	No adsorption
	60.0		3.2	10.0	8.8	7.0	7.0		
	40.0		1.5	7.4	6.0	4.7	6.0		
	30.0		0.8	6.0	4.5	3.6	4.0		
	20.0		0.5	4.3	3.0	2.5	3.0		
	10.0		—	2.5	1.0	1.2	1.0		

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherms of p-nitrophenol from solution in dioxane on alumina of varying pH.

FIG 2 Adsorption isotherms of PNP and ONP from methanol soln. on alumina of varying pH.

- v) The desorption data (not shown separately) reveal that the mono-nitrophenols adsorbed on alumina from benzene could be desorbed sufficiently with methanol. Thus PNP, MNP and ONP could be desorbed to the extent of 80%, 75% and 60% respectively.

vi) The solutes adsorbed from dioxane on alumina (pH 11.5) are desorbed quantitatively with water and 0.1 *N* aq. NaOH.

The pK_a of these sorbates lies in the range 7.0-8.5 (PNP 7.20, MNP 8.40 and ONP 7.17). It means that at $pH < 7.0$, the molecular species of the solutes should predominate in solution and at $pH > 7.0$ mainly the anions should be involved in adsorption. As pH of the substrate increases above the pK_a value, more of the anionic species are generated, which are not soluble in the non-aqueous solvents (dioxane, benzene) and hence adsorbed.

The isotherms for ONP and PNP are of L- and S-shape (Figs. 1 and 2). PNP from dioxane at pH 11.5 has L_1 -type isotherm which assumes rather S-shape at pH 6.0-8.6. ONP also gives S-type curve from dioxane at pH 11.5 (not shown). Thus, the mechanism of adsorption may well differ according to the history of alumina surface⁸.

It is likely that weak chemical interactions may occur between the free-OH groups of alumina surface and the anionic species in the favourable range of adsorption ($pH > 7.0$). At pH values below their pK_a , solute-solute interactions (e.g., hydrogen bonding) may occur affecting adsorption. This is also indicated by the change in the nature of isotherms from L- to S-type.

The low affinity of ONP as compared to PNP may be due to chelation. The behaviour of MNP is rather typical, which needs further investigation.

Chromatographic Separation of ONP, MNP and PNP :

Our aim in the above short study has been to find out suitable conditions for the column chromatography of these isomeric nitrophenols. The separation is based on the quantitative adsorption of the compounds from benzene by alumina of pH 11.5 (Table 2), and the varying adsorption-desorption (and hence migration) with dioxane containing methanol.

Glass column (10×1 cm) was packed dry with Brockmann alumina of pH 11.5 to a column height of 8 cm. 5.0 ml each of the nitrophenol solution in benzene (80 mg/l) were withdrawn, mixed, applied to the column, and kept as such for an hour. On developing the chromatogram with 30 ml of dioxane-methanol (19 : 1, v/v) three distinct bands could be seen upper canary-yellow band of PNP (0.5 cm width), colourless space (0.5 cm), light golden-yellow band of MNP (1 cm), colourless space (2 cm), and then the orange-yellow band of ONP (2 cm). This shows a clear-cut separation of the solutes. The separation was more distinct with further 10 ml of

the developer. ONP could be removed with 20 ml of dioxane-methanol (9 : 1, v/v.) MNP was eluted out of the column with further addition of 30 ml of the eluent. PNP was eluted with 20 ml of dioxane-methanol (1 : 1, v/v). The eluate fractions were determined colorimetrically by developing colour with alkali, as described earlier.

The recoveries were quantitative for ONP and PNP and 99.9% for MNP.

Distribution studies and separation :

The distribution coefficients (K_d) for desorption of the solutes adsorbed from benzene were determined ($ml\ g^{-1}$) after equilibrating alumina (0.25 g, pH 11.5) with 25 ml benzene solution (80 mg/l) for one hour at $30 \pm 1^\circ$. After draining out benzene completely, the adsorbed solutes were shaken with 25 ml of the eluent (mixture of dioxane-methanol of varying proportions) for 24 hr, and the desorbed quantity estimated colorimetrically. The values are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3— K_d VALUES FOR ONP, MNP AND PNP.

Solute	K_d values, $ml\ g^{-1}$, in dioxane-methanol (v/v).		
	19:1	9:1	1:1
PNP	56.2	53.1	41.3
MNP	247.3	152.8	100.0
ONP	133.3	91.4	47.0

A review of Table 3 shows that MNP has the highest K_d value in the developer (19 : 1, dioxane-methanol). It is, therefore, expected that in the ternary separation, MNP should form the upper-most band of the chromatogram. However, it occupies the middle portion of the chromatogram, as described earlier. As per the adsorption behaviour, MNP is expected to occupy the lower-most band, as it has no adsorption in these solvents. Hence, the combined effect of the two forces of adsorption and desorption determine the migration rate. The effect is maximum on ONP.

References

1. L. R. SNYDER, *J. Chromatog.*, 1966, 23, 388.
2. M. J. FULLER, *Chromatogr. Review*, 1971, 14, 45.
3. G. L. MUNDHARA and J. S. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 1033.
4. G. L. MUNDHARA and J. S. TIWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (In press).
5. J. S. JAIN and V. L. SHOYINK, *J. of Water Pollution Control*, 1973, 45, 2463.
6. J. S. MATSON and H. B. MARK (Jr), *J. of Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1969, 31(1), 1916.
7. C. H. GILES, A. P. D'SILVA and A. S. TRIVEDI, *J. of Appl. Chem. (London)*, 1970, 20, 37.
8. C. H. GILES, A. P. D'SILVA and I. A. EASTON, *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1974, 47, 755.